

Energy-efficient AI-ready Data Spaces

Connecting Data Spaces: A practical approach using the Sovity Connector

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Preface: BDVA strategic context and alignment

The Big Data Value Association (BDVA) aims to foster a vibrant ecosystem for data and AI innovation that is aligned with European values and delivers positive impact for business, society, and policymaking. To this end, breaking silos and fostering interoperability among data ecosystems is one of BDVA's key objectives. This objective is explicitly reflected in BDVA's Strategic Agenda under the theme "[Expanding data-driven ecosystems across sectors and \(global\) value chains](#)." [1]

The Green.Dat.AI project has actively contributed to this objective, and demonstrated strong engagement through proactive participation and substantial contributions to different BDVA activities, particularly those focused on data sharing and data space functionalities.

More specifically, the work presented in this document shows an open-source-based approach to achieving a first level of interoperability between two data spaces, being able to authenticate and exchange data while keeping their own identity managers. In this sense, the work is fully aligned with BDVA objectives, since it fosters cross-sector and cross-domain interoperability, relies on open, standard-based, and reusable components, helping to reduce fragmentation, and facilitates the participation of SMEs and smaller actors in data ecosystems.

BDVA considers the contribution of the Green.Dat.AI project to its activities as an example of good practice in collaboration between the association and EU-funded R&I projects, resulting in mutual benefits for both.

— Big Data Value Association

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Background: The Two Data Spaces.....	4
2.1. Green.Dat.AI Data Space.....	4
2.2. DISCO Data Space.....	5
3. Motivation for Integration.....	6
3.1. DISCO Federation Component.....	8
4. Implementation and testing.....	8
4.1. High-Level Architecture.....	8
4.2. Testing Procedure.....	9
4.3. Results and Observations.....	11
5. Conclusion.....	11
6. Bibliography.....	12

1. Introduction

Data spaces are rapidly emerging across sectors as organisations seek more controlled, sovereign, and semantically rich ways to share data, following principles articulated by initiatives such as the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) [2], which emphasise interoperability, data sovereignty, and trusted data sharing. From energy and mobility to agriculture and urban logistics, initiatives are developing their own governance models and technical stacks. Yet despite this growth, interoperability between data spaces remains limited, with most operating as isolated islands, restricting cross-domain data flows and preventing the creation of broader value chains and integrated services. Achieving interoperability has therefore become a central challenge for the next generation of data-sharing infrastructures.

For Green.Dat.AI [3], interoperability is essential to realise its full impact and vision. Data today is generated and stored in diverse systems across organisations and domains; without seamless communication between them, its value remains fragmented. Interoperability enables trusted collaboration, allowing stakeholders to share datasets and insights under clear control and governance. This contributes to richer analytics, stronger AI models, and better-informed decision-making.

Practical benefits also arise from efficiency. Interoperable systems avoid duplicated work, reduce inconsistencies, and make it easier to reuse existing resources, particularly important for SMEs targeted by Green.Dat.AI, who often lack the capacity to build and maintain complex data infrastructure. Most importantly, interoperability fuels innovation: when data from different sectors can interact meaningfully, it enables new services, business models, and cross-domain AI applications that support greener and more resilient digital ecosystems.

By adopting common standards and ensuring compatibility with other data spaces, Green.Dat.AI contributes to the wider European data ecosystem and supports the goals of the European Data Strategy. This vision motivated our test scenario: to investigate whether full, end-to-end interoperability between two independently operated data spaces could be achieved in practice. We tested this with the Urban Freight Data Space from the DISCO project [4], which has developed a federated identity management component enabling connectors to interact securely while using different authentication providers. By integrating this component into both data spaces, we demonstrated “true” interoperability using readily available open-source software, allowing each data space to maintain its own identity manager and configuration while securely exchanging data.

The remainder of this paper introduces the two projects and their architectural approaches (Section 2), outlines the motivation for this testing and the tools used (Section 3), describes the implementation and presents key lessons learned (Section 4), and concludes with final reflections (Section 5).

2. Background: The Two Data Spaces

2.1. Green.Dat.AI Data Space

The Green.Dat.AI Data Space (DS) has been designed to enable controlled data and service exchange between providers and consumers without exposing data directly. Instead, a data space connector acts as a proxy: the provider’s connector fetches data from its source, and the consumer’s connector receives it and forwards it to any chosen data sink, whether publicly exposed or protected. This approach offers flexibility to both sides. Providers can choose which parts of their data to expose and under what access conditions, without sharing direct credentials; consumers can ingest the received data into any system they operate.

To use the Green.Dat.AI DS, each participant must deploy their own connector, which functions as their unique access point to the environment. Connectors enforce data sovereignty by design, protecting internal

systems while ensuring secure and efficient data transfer between participants; this can be seen in Figure 1 where Green.Dat.AI DS is the bridge enabling data exchange between providers and consumers of data and services.

Trusted interaction in the Green.Dat.AI DS is enforced through a Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS), where all connectors must be registered. The DAPS manages participant identities and issues the security tokens required to perform actions such as contract negotiation and data consumption. Furthermore, a Catalogue component complements this process by exposing metadata provided by participants and supporting contract negotiation. Once an agreement is established, the consumer can securely obtain the provider's dataset through its connector.

Within Green.Dat.AI, the above-mentioned components are implemented using parametrised forks of Sovity's open-source stack: the Sovity EDC Community Edition 7.2.1 as the connector, a customised version of Sovity EDC UI 3.2.2 as the Connector UI, and Sovity DAPS 23.0.7 for identity management. [5]

2.2. DISCO Data Space

The DISCO project (Horizon Europe-funded initiative with grant agreement No 101103954) focuses on advancing data-driven innovation in urban freight by building a modular, interoperable, and standards-aligned Urban Freight Data Space (UFDS). Its objective is to enable cities, logistics stakeholders, and service providers to share data securely under clear governance rules while preserving data sovereignty. To achieve this, DISCO develops core data space components, semantic models, and a set of reference applications that demonstrate how cross-stakeholder data exchange can support more efficient, sustainable, and resilient urban logistics operations. A central part of the project is ensuring that the UFDS remains interoperable with other emerging data spaces; towards this goal, a federated data space component has been implemented, enabling connectors governed by different identity and trust providers to interact seamlessly while maintaining their independent governance and configuration.

As of December 2025, the UFDS is built from several key components. It uses the Sovity Connector (v10.4.4) and a UFDS UI based on a fork of Sovity UI v4.1.7. Identity management is provided through a Keycloak-DAPS setup, derived from Sovity's Keycloak v25.0.3-1 but updated to a newer Keycloak version. For semantic support, the UFDS includes a Vocabulary Hub based on a fork of TNO's Semantic Treehouse v3.6. The UFDS also includes an in-house Logging House, with a client deployed next to each connector and a server run by the Data Space Authority; both are implemented as FastAPI Python services, with the client also using an Apache APISIX API gateway. A similar setup forms the Broker mechanism, with a Subscriber at each connector and a Publisher at the Data Space Authority. Finally, and relevant to this paper, the UFDS features a federated data space component that allows connectors to communicate with connectors from other data spaces that use different identity managers. This component consists of a FastAPI Python service and an Apache APISIX API gateway, and its detailed design and functionality has been covered in a previous publication. [6] An overview of the UFDS architecture is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Green.Dat.AI Data Space - High Level Architecture [7]

3. Motivation for Integration

The Green.Dat.AI DS connector provides the technological compatibility needed to handle different data formats and structures while ensuring privacy and security, two major concerns that often prevent organisations from sharing data. By following IDSA standards, the connector enables seamless interaction with other connectors and data services across the IDS ecosystem, regardless of the underlying technology. Cryptographic mechanisms secure identities and data integrity, while Catalogue and Vocabulary services ensure that data can be recognised and interpreted consistently.

Figure 2: DISCO Data Space - High Level Architecture [8]

For Green.Dat.AI, interoperability is not simply a feature but a strategic requirement. Its value depends on the ability to integrate with other data spaces so that stakeholders, especially SMEs, can access trusted, efficient, and cost-effective data-driven solutions. Without interoperability, data remains siloed, onboarding and integration costs increase, and access to cross-domain information is limited. Green.Dat.AI addresses this by reducing technical and business barriers to data sharing, supporting new business models, and lowering dependence on custom development or vendor-specific technologies.

Technically, the connector acts as a bridge between heterogeneous systems, supporting multiple data formats and protocols while enforcing strict privacy and security measures suitable for multi-stakeholder environments. In essence, interoperability allows Green.Dat.AI to operate as a federated, scalable, and trustworthy data space that integrates naturally into Europe’s wider data ecosystem, maximising impact and enabling alignment with current and future sectoral data spaces.

When evaluating connectors for our data space, the Sovity Connector stood out for its technical maturity, clear deployment process, intuitive UI, and the accompanying Sovity DAPS, which provides a straightforward trust and identity layer. Its open-source nature also made code inspection and adaptation easy.

A major limitation, however, was its inability to operate with more than one identity manager (DAPS) at the same time. This prevented real interoperability between independent data spaces. The only workaround was to “migrate” a connector from data space A to the DAPS of data space B, allowing it to interact there but effectively removing it from A and blocking simultaneous participation in both. This pseudo-federation fell short of the multi data space setup we aimed for.

Since adopting a different connector with decentralized identity support would have required significant effort, DISCO’s federation component offered a practical alternative. It allowed us to keep the Sovity

Connector while enabling connectors governed by different DAPS to interact without reconfiguration or migration, achieving the level of federation we were aiming for.

Our integration objective was deliberately simple: confirm whether two connectors, each using an X.509 certificate from its own data space's DAPS, could authenticate, publish a dataset across data spaces, and successfully consume it. No additional functionality was tested; the goal was solely to validate basic, end-to-end trusted interoperability without altering the connectors' native identity setup.

In Section 3.1, we give a brief overview of how DISCO's federation component works and how it enables federation between data spaces. This description is intentionally concise, as a full technical explanation is already available in a separate open-access publication. Error! Bookmark not defined.

3.1. DISCO Federation Component

The DISCO Federation Component is a proof-of-concept extension to the Sovity Connector that removes its single-DAPS limitation (in the standard Sovity setup, all connectors must authenticate against the same identity manager). The Federation Component enables a decentralised setup by allowing a connector to trust and validate tokens from multiple DAPS, making cross-data space federation possible using only open-source tools.

Developed for DISCO's needs in the urban-freight context, the component acts as a lightweight wrapper around the Sovity Connector. It relies on two elements: an Apache APISIX gateway that intercepts incoming requests, and a Python FastAPI webserver (Federation Plugin) that provides the public keys of all trusted DAPS in the federation and performs required token validations. Instead of contacting a single DAPS during startup, the connector retrieves the combined keyset from the Federation Plugin, enabling it to authenticate participants from different data spaces. Furthermore, the plugin carries out additional token validation checks designed to strengthen the trust mechanism at the federation level.

This approach directly addresses the identity-centralisation issue that prevents practical interoperability. It allows each organisation to retain its own identity management while choosing which external DAPS to trust, avoiding the need to merge data spaces under a single authority. A full technical description of the component can be found in a separate open-access publication [6], and the plugin's codebase is open sourced. [9]

4. Implementation and testing

4.1. High-Level Architecture

To set up the testing environment, we relied on the existing deployments of both data spaces. Since the purpose was strictly experimental, we deployed one additional connector in each data space, along with the two federation components described in Section 3.1. Each deployment was composed of six containers: (1) the Sovity Connector, (2) the Sovity UI, (3) the PostgreSQL used by the connector, (4) an OAuth2Proxy for secure UI login, (5) an Apache APISIX gateway, and (6) the Federation Plugin's FastAPI server.

When deploying the connectors and to align with how the Federation Component operates, we ensured that the new connectors' IDs included the "issuer value" of their respective DAPS, that is, the value of the iss claim embedded in issued tokens. Thus, each ID followed the structure <issuer-value>:<connector-name>. Hence, DISCO's connector identifier became: `https://daps.disco.inlecom.gr:7443/realms/DAPS:federation_test`, while Green.Dat.AI's one was `https://keycloak-daps.greendatai.ari-energy.eu/realms/DAPS:federation_test`.

A simplified high-level representation of the test architecture is shown in Figure 3, where for clarity each data space is illustrated with three connectors: two pre-existing ones plus the test connector; moreover, the connector identifiers are shortened for clarity but still emphasising the transition from a simple connector ID to the format <issuer-value>:<connector-name>.

Figure 3: High Level Testing Architecture (simplified)

4.2. Testing Procedure

Before beginning the test, we added a dataset to each deployed connector. For simplicity, we used real-time temperature data retrieved from the Open-Meteo API; Madrid, Spain for Green.Dat.AI and Athens, Greece for DISCO.¹ Afterwards, the administrators of both data spaces exchanged the public keys published by their respective DAPS instances (accessible through each deployment’s JWKS URL). The full interaction and testing flow is shown in Figure 4.

¹ As an example, https://api.open-meteo.com/v1/forecast?latitude=37.98&longitude=23.73¤t=temperature_2m provides the current temperature in Athens.

Figure 4: Federated Data Space Integration Testing Flowchart

A key part of this flow is Step 8, which is required to prevent a scenario where a malicious DAPS operator could generate valid-looking tokens on behalf of any connector across both data spaces. This step limits trust

strictly to connectors belonging to the data space of the issuing DAPS. Specifically, once the DAPS-issued token has been intercepted (Step 6) and forwarded to the Federation Component's FastAPI server (Step 7), the validation in Step 8 proceeds as follows:

1. Decode the received token and extract the kid value from the headers, indicating the key signing it.
2. Check if kid exists exactly once in the Federation Component database (otherwise, validation fails).
3. Retrieve the iss value associated with that kid from the database and compare it with the iss claim in the token (must match, otherwise validation fails).
4. Extract the sub claim (the connector ID with format <issuer-value>:<connector-name>) and verify that the issuer portion of this ID matches the iss value (otherwise, validation fails).
5. If all checks pass, return HTTP 200 OK to the API Gateway, authorising the request to be forwarded to the Sovity Connector.

For further information on this design please consult a previous publication. [6]

4.3. Results and Observations

The testing proceeded smoothly, and data exchange between the two data spaces was successful without any integration issues. This outcome was largely due to DISCO's Federation Component having already been tested internally within DISCO before this experiment, and to our decision to align the Sovity Connector versions across both data spaces.² Deploying dedicated connectors for the test also avoided potential legacy configuration conflicts.

Cross-data space trust establishment worked as intended. The exchange of public keys from both DAPS instances, combined with the Federation Component's validation logic, enabled mutual authentication without additional tuning. Moreover, both connectors were publicly reachable by each other, eliminating network complications that could have otherwise arisen.

Our main practical insight relates to the connector IDs used and their readability. Because each ID embeds the full DAPS issuer value, the resulting names are long and URL-like. A more usable alternative would be to assign short nicknames to each DAPS-issued public key loaded into the federation component (e.g., greendatai and disco), which would require only a minor schema adjustment in the Federation Component database and to the 5-step procedure described above.

5. Conclusion

This work demonstrated that data spaces operating under different identity managers can successfully authenticate and exchange data without (much) reconfiguration or loss of sovereignty. By combining the Sovity Connector with DISCO's Federation Component, we achieved practical, end-to-end interoperability using only open-source software and minimal deployment effort. The results confirm that secure data space federation is not merely a theoretical concept but can be implemented today with existing tools.

² We downgraded DISCO's testing connector and UI to match Green.Dat.AI's version (see Section 2 for version details).

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